

Evaluating the Performance of Large Language Models on the MCAT

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Abstract: The emergence of large language models (LLMs) such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT and Google’s Gemini has opened new possibilities for their use in standardized test preparation. This study evaluates the performance of ChatGPT 4.0 and Gemini (both December 2024 versions) on an official AAMC full-length Medical College Admission Test (MCAT) practice exam. Using a standardized input protocol, we compared the models’ answers and calculated accuracy, MCAT section scores, and percentile rankings. ChatGPT outperformed Gemini, achieving a score of 522 (99th percentile) with an accuracy of 90.87%, compared to Gemini’s 518 (95th percentile) and 84.78% accuracy, with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.005$). While these results highlight the educational potential of LLMs, they also raise important questions about the relevance of standardized testing in an era of increasingly accessible AI tools. Furthermore, although LLMs perform well on exams, their non-negligible error rates caution against their use in clinical decision-making without human oversight. This study contributes to the growing discussion on how AI may transform medical education, assessment, and the future role of physicians.

Keywords: AI, MCAT, large language models, standardized exams, ChatGPT, Gemini

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid innovation of artificial intelligence in the 21st century has led to the development of language learning models, also known as large language models (LLMs), which serve as a versatile tool with multiple capabilities. They utilize deep learning models pre-trained on vast amounts of data, combined with a neural network, to comprehend the meanings of a sequence of text and identify the relationships between the words within it [1]. Particularly, two leading language learning models are OpenAI’s ChatGPT and Google’s Gemini. ChatGPT is recognized for its ability to identify patterns in data and synthesize them into coherent, naturally sounding text. Google describes its AI model Gemini as a “multimodal” model, with the ability to generate and understand multiple types of information, including text, code, audio, images, and video [2]. Given their rapid advancement and expanding capabilities, large language models are increasingly being explored for applications in education, including standardized test preparation.

OpenAI’s GPT-4 technical report from 2023 revealed that the model scored in the 90th percentile on the Uniform Bar Exam for lawyers and in the 88th percentile on the Law School Admission Test (LSAT) [3]. The model also got a 5, which is the highest given

score, on many of College Board’s Advanced Placement exams, including Biology, Art History, Environmental Sciences, Macro and Microeconomics, Statistics, and many more. This report further underscores ChatGPT’s potential as a high-performing educational tool. However, the report does not evaluate GPT-4 on the Medical College Admission Test (MCAT) or other interdisciplinary, reasoning-intensive science exams, showing the gap in understanding on how these models perform on tests that more closely mirror the cognitive demands of medical education—an area this study seeks to address.

A number of studies have already evaluated LLM performance on medical and standardized exams. Kung et al. demonstrated that ChatGPT-3.5 achieved 75% accuracy on Step 1 exam, 61.5% on Step 2 exam, and 68.8% on Step 3 exam of the United States Medical Licensing Examination (USMLE), all of which are passing scores, suggesting its potential in medical education [4]. Similarly, Gilson et al. found that ChatGPT could pass National Board of Medical Examiners (NBME) style questions with plausible and educationally valuable explanations, and achieved a passing score on the free NBME Step 1 questions, though limitations remained in clinical nuance and reliability [5].

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While these studies focused on LLMs' ability to answer knowledge-based medical questions, other research has begun exploring their performance on assessments of professional judgment and soft skills. Chu et al. compared the responses of ChatGPT and Google Gemini to those expected on the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) PREview situational judgment test, which is designed to assess core professional competencies like cultural sensitivity, ethical responsibility, and teamwork [6]. The findings highlighted that while AI could mimic thoughtful responses in structured scenarios, significant limitations remain in truly understanding context, empathy, and moral nuances, reinforcing the importance of human judgment in professional evaluations. Another such test, the Medical College Admission Test (MCAT), presents a unique challenge for LLMs due to its heavy emphasis on critical reasoning, passage interpretation, and interdisciplinary scientific knowledge. The MCAT is a standardized, multiple-choice exam administered by the AAMC, a critical component of the medical school admissions process in the United States and Canada. The test is formatted primarily with passages followed by sets of questions based on these passages, with some independent questions that do not correspond to any passages [7]. The test is broken into 4 sections: Chemical and Physical Foundations of Biological Systems, Critical Analysis and Reasoning Skills (CARS), Biological and Biochemical Foundations of Living Systems, and Psychological, Social, and Biological Foundations of Behavior [7]. Prior research has demonstrated ChatGPT's strong performance on the MCAT, achieving scores in the top percentiles across multiple test sections. One such study, Bommineni et al., assessed ChatGPT's performance on an AAMC sample exam from October 2022 [8]. They found the model had an accuracy of 50% in Chemical and Physical Foundations and 75% in the other 3 sections. Their study showed that LLMs can perform competitively and generate explanations that could support personalized learning. This suggests that LLMs may be leveraged to support more personalized and equitable approaches to premedical education by providing high-quality, accessible tutoring and feedback for students from diverse educational backgrounds. However, there is a lack of literature testing Google Gemini's ability on the MCAT.

Building on this foundation, our study seeks to address a key gap in the literature: the absence of direct comparisons between leading LLMs—specifically ChatGPT and Google Gemini. This study aims to compare ChatGPT 4.0 and Google Gemini's abilities to

accurately answer questions on the MCAT exam. Their performance on an official AAMC full-length MCAT practice test will be used to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference in accuracy between the two models. In doing so, we aim to assess their respective strengths and limitations across the exam's four sections. This analysis offers insights into the potential utility of large language models as educational tools for MCAT preparation, contributing to the broader discussion on their role in medical education and the relevance of the MCAT in an era of increased AI use.

II. Methodology

The objective of this study was to evaluate the accuracy of the large language models ChatGPT 4.0 (December 2024 version) and Google Gemini (December 2024 version) on a full-length MCAT practice exam and determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in their performance. We selected the MCAT Official Prep Free Practice Exam, which is widely regarded as one of the most representative and predictive practice assessments available for the MCAT, using questions from previously administered MCAT exams [9]. Most students preparing to take the MCAT take this test due to its close alignment with the official test in structure, content, scoring methodology, and being the official practice exam from the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC).

Each section of the exam, including the passage-based format that is characteristic of the MCAT, was faithfully preserved. Passages and their associated multiple-choice questions were entered into each AI model sequentially. Both ChatGPT and Gemini were prompted with the passage content, followed by each corresponding question, one at a time, to replicate the format and constraints faced by human test-takers. After obtaining the responses from each AI model, we recorded the selected answers and submitted them to the official AAMC online scoring system to generate an accuracy percentage, individual section scores, and total MCAT scores. To evaluate the statistical significance between the performances of the two models, we compared the number of correct responses using a two-proportion z-test. To contextualize these scores, we converted them into percentile ranks using the official 2024 MCAT score percentiles published by the AAMC.

III. RESULTS

The scores are reported using the AAMC MCAT 2024 scoring scale, where each section is scored from

118–132, and the total score ranges from 472–528. The percentile ranks were derived from the official AAMC 2024 MCAT percentile chart [10]. In a comparison of performance on MCAT-style questions, Gemini outperformed ChatGPT in terms of overall accuracy. Out of 230 questions, Chat GPT answered 209 correctly (90.87%), whereas Gemini answered 195 correctly (84.78%), with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.005$). When broken down into individual sections, both models scored 131 in the Critical Analysis and Reasoning Skills (CARS) section, corresponding to the 99th percentile, and 130 in the Biology and Biochemistry section, placing them at the 96th percentile. In Chemistry and Physics, Chat GPT scored 130 (96th percentile) compared to Gemini's 128 (85th percentile). In the Psychology and Sociology section, Chat GPT scored 131 (97th percentile), while Gemini scored 129 (85th percentile). These sectional differences contributed to Chat GPT achieving a composite MCAT score of 522 (99th percentile), while Gemini scored 518 (95th percentile).

Groups	Total Questions	Number Correct	% Correct	P-value
Chat GPT	230	209	90.87	0.0051
Gemini	230	195	84.78	

A. **Table 1**

Accuracy Comparison Between ChatGPT and Gemini on a Full-Length MCAT Practice Test. The number of questions answered correctly out of 230 total questions is our accuracy, and the p-value was calculated using a two-proportion z-test to evaluate the statistical significance between the two models' performance

Groups	Chemistry & Physics	CARS	Biology & Biochemistry	Psychology & Sociology	MCAT Score
Chat GPT	130	131	130	131	522
Chat GPT Percentile	96th	99th	96th	97th	99th
Gemini	128	131	130	129	518
Gemini Percentile	85th	99th	96th	85th	95th

B. **Table 2**

MCAT Section Scores and Percentiles for ChatGPT and Gemini. The scores are reported using the AAMC

MCAT 2024 scoring scale, where each section is scored from 118–132, and the total score ranges from 472–528. The percentile ranks were derived from the official AAMC 2024 MCAT percentile chart [10].

IV. DISCUSSION

While the performance of large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT and Gemini on the MCAT is impressive, they do have limitations. In our study, ChatGPT had a 90.87% accuracy, and Gemini scored slightly lower, with an accuracy of 84.78%. These results demonstrate that while LLMs can achieve top-tier standardized test scores, they are not infallible. A 9–15% error rate might be acceptable or even excellent in a testing environment, but if applied to clinical decision-making, a 15% rate of misdiagnoses and wrong treatments can have severe consequences. This reinforces the need for caution when considering the application of AI tools in diagnostic or treatment-related settings.

When evaluated on the MCAT Official Prep Free Practice Exam, both ChatGPT and Gemini demonstrated notable difficulty in interpreting visual data, particularly graphs. The majority of incorrect responses were associated with questions that required graphical interpretation. For example, in Passage 5 (Question 196) of the exam, ChatGPT misinterpreted the data points in a bar graph illustrating the effects of various drug treatments for Alzheimer's disease.

An interesting observation is that Gemini demonstrates greater confidence in its responses than ChatGPT, even when it is incorrect. In Passage 7 (Q36, KiK_iKi of MCS oligomers), ChatGPT acknowledged its mistake after being informed of the error, stating, 'I misread the semi-log x-axis... eyeballed 0.17 μM (170 nM)... the halfway drop is actually closer to 3×10^{-8} M (~30 nM).' It then corrected its answer.

In contrast, in Passage 5 (Q23–26), Gemini incorrectly selected option B instead of the correct C. When challenged, it defended its choice, arguing that the test favored treatment-to-treatment comparisons over patient-to-control outcomes, rather than reconsidering its initial selection. This response highlights Gemini's tendency, unlike ChatGPT, to maintain an incorrect stance by attributing the error to the framing of the question, rather than reevaluating its reasoning

On the other hand, ChatGPT maintains its position when challenged on a question it has answered correctly. For example, in a gas law problem, ChatGPT initially reasoned accurately, stating, "Double PPP

halves VVV, not doubles it.” When prompted with a challenge, it remained firm in its response, suggesting instead that the input itself might have been erroneous.

These findings also challenge the foundational assumption that standardized tests like the MCAT are effective tools for identifying future physicians. These models offer valuable support in educational contexts, but their existence also challenges us to rethink traditional assessments and how we define readiness and competence in medicine. Publicly accessible AI models score in the top percentiles, questioning the value of the MCAT as a measure of individual competence or readiness for medical school. As access to AI tools becomes ubiquitous, we may need to re-evaluate whether the MCAT still serves its intended purpose as a differentiating factor among applicants. This development mirrors shifts in education in the past. For example, calculators were once banned from standardized tests like the SAT, but are now standard on tests [11]. Perhaps AI, like the calculator, will eventually be seen not as a shortcut, but accepted as a standard tool—one that future pre-medical students should be trained to use responsibly. These results suggest that it may be time to reevaluate how we assess readiness for medical training. Incorporating more holistic measures—such as interpersonal skills, ethical reasoning, resilience, and real-world problem-solving—could offer a more accurate picture of who is best suited to meet the complex demands of modern medicine.

Despite these insights from our study, there are several limitations. Our analysis was limited to a single full-length MCAT practice test, which may not capture the full range of difficulty or variation present across different tests. Our results may not fully generalize to the entire content spectrum or future versions of the exam. Secondly, the study evaluated the models in ideal conditions, with no time constraints on each question or test fatigue, whereas human test-takers are influenced by stress, time pressure, and stamina. Third, while care was taken to replicate the passage-based nature of the exam, LLMs lack other unique test-taking strategies or prioritization skills that influence human performance. Additionally, the study focused solely on answer accuracy and did not evaluate the reasoning processes or justifications provided by the AI, which are critical in assessing their reliability in educational or clinical contexts. Finally, because LLMs are continuously evolving, their performance may change rapidly over time, with new versions coming out, making it important to interpret the findings as a snapshot rather than a definitive evaluation of long-term capabilities.

As increasing amounts of large language models (LLMs) are integrated into academic learning, their usage in educational and clinical settings raises significant legal and ethical concerns. The accessibility of tools like ChatGPT and Google Gemini in standardized testing presents challenges to academic integrity. If applicants are able to leverage LLMs to prepare for or simulate MCAT-style questions, it may compromise the test's ability to reflect individual aptitude. The MCAT itself has been questioned for its alleged inequity, and the initial implementation of the MCAT in 1928 has also been criticised for its targeting of Black schools, closing around 70% of traditionally Black medical schools and standardizing them to an all-white model [12].

The wide accessibility of LLMs introduces concerns about fairness and equity, particularly for students without comparable access to advanced AI tools. Institutions must imperatively consider developing clear guidelines for acceptable AI use in admissions-related assessments to ensure a level playing field.

In clinical contexts, the legal implications become even more consequential. The potential use of LLMs in supporting diagnostic or treatment decisions prompts critical questions about liability. If an AI system provides incorrect or harmful medical advice that is not accurate, determining legal responsibility remains ambiguous. The usage of LLMs in other fields, such as law, has already demonstrated the dangers of putting full trust in a software. In a case where a man sued an airline for an injury, his lawyers were sanctioned for using imaginary cases in a brief, each being generated by ChatGPT [13]. Current regulatory frameworks do not fully address the attribution of fault in AI-assisted medical decisions, leaving gaps in legal accountability that may affect both patients and practitioners. Until these frameworks are updated, healthcare institutions and technology developers must proceed with caution and ensure that AI remains a decision-support tool under the oversight of qualified professionals.

Although LLMs raise important ethical and legal concerns, they also hold promise for improving educational access and quality. AI tools can provide personalized, on-demand tutoring that adapts to a student's pace and knowledge, as well as adapt to a student's preferred learning style [14]. This can be beneficial for students in under-resourced schools who may not have access to expensive prep courses or private tutors as their other competitors may. AI can also generate high-quality practice questions and offer

immediate feedback. If used responsibly, AI could help widen access to high-quality test preparation and promote educational equity, as well as help to create an AI-ready population rather than diminish educational and social possibilities [15].

In clinical practice, AI systems have the potential to enhance patient care and physician efficiency. LLMs can assist in clinical decision-making by rapidly synthesizing vast amounts of medical literature, suggesting possible diagnoses, and flagging potential treatment conflicts or rare conditions that may be overlooked. AI systems can also assist in reading medical images to detect abnormalities. Healthcare providers can spend more time on direct patient care as administrative tasks such as patient histories, drafting clinical notes, and managing bills can all be completed by a LLM. Clinicians at Stanford Health Care were introduced to an AI app that could assist with clinical notes. As Dr. Christopher Sharp noted, practitioners appreciated the technology because they were now able to “turn away from my keyboard, face the patient and really listen, knowing that everything shared in our conversation was being documented” [16]. This goes to highlight the benefits of integrating AI in real healthcare systems. In rural or underserved regions, AI-powered telemedicine could also extend specialist expertise to areas lacking trained professionals, helping to close care gaps.

The integration of large language models into both academic and clinical settings offers unprecedented opportunities to expand access, improve efficiency, and enhance a doctor’s decision making. Yet, they also introduce ethical and legal challenges. In education, LLMs could either deepen existing inequities or help level the playing field by providing high quality test-preparation to all demographics. Depending on how institutions regulate their use, LLMs could be transformative in the education field. In real-life healthcare practice, AI has the ability to transform patient care by allowing doctors to spend more time on actual care while administrative tasks can be completed by AI. AI can also interpret scans and provide diagnoses that can supplement a doctor’s differential [17]. However, harmful errors can be introduced with an unclear legal pathway. By taking proactive measures now to ensure the integrity of LLM systems, healthcare systems can utilize AI’s benefits while ensuring the sincerity that is demanded by the profession.

This development prompts reflection on the continued use of knowledge and memorization-based assessments like medical board exams. A lot of the information tested can now be retrieved instantly by AI,

so future assessments should focus more on clinical reasoning, communication, and ethical decision-making—skills that are unique to humans and essential for physicians. Future research could explore the performance of LLMs across many MCAT exams. Expanding the scope to include a wider variety of LLMs developed by different companies and countries would also provide a more comprehensive understanding of the capabilities, limitations, and educational utility of different AI across platforms. Additionally, studies should assess the educational outcomes for students using LLMs as study aids and investigate how these tools might be equitably integrated into premedical preparation.

V. CONCLUSION

Future research should examine the performance of large language models (LLMs) across a broader range of MCAT examinations and expand comparative analyses to include models developed by different companies and countries. Such efforts would provide a more comprehensive understanding of their capabilities, limitations, and potential educational utility. Additionally, investigations into the effects of LLM use on student learning outcomes and strategies for equitable integration into premedical preparation are warranted. At the same time, the broader influence of artificial intelligence on education and healthcare raises important considerations. While LLMs demonstrate an accuracy rate of approximately 85–90%, this corresponds to a potential error margin of up to 15%, which far exceeds the generally accepted 3% threshold in medical practice. These findings underscore the necessity of exercising caution when incorporating AI into contexts where accuracy and reliability are paramount. AI should function as an adjunctive tool rather than a replacement for physician judgment in medical diagnosis and treatment, and questions of legal liability for AI-associated errors must be addressed as these technologies continue to evolve and proliferate.

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